

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha, 2 h d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2.3 kg ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Lateefy, a new aromatic semidwarf rice

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In 1983 Pakistan released Lateefy, an aromatic semidwarf rice, for general cultivation in Sind Province. It was developed at the RRI in Dokri. It is expected to replace local tall, scented Sugdasi and Basmati rices.

Lateefy is from a cross between IRRI line IR760-A1-22-2-3 and Basmati 370, a tall, scented variety from Punjab. Selec-

tion emphasized semidwarf plant type, grain characters, aroma, and early maturity. The selected line (IR760-A1-22-2-3/Basmati 370)-6-2-2-1 was tested at Dokri and in farmers' fields. It performed significantly better than Jajai 77, a leading scented tall Sugdasi type, and Basmati 370.

Lateefy yields twice more than Jajai 77 and Basmati 370, has more stem borer resistance, and matures 3 wk earlier. Grain quality equals or surpasses that of those varieties (see table). Lateefy is expected to meet local and export standards for aromatic rice. □

Comparative qualities of Lateefy, Jajai 77, and Basmati 370.

Character	Lateefy	Jajai 77	Basmati 370
Plant height (cm)	109	176	172
Maturity (d)	126	142	147
Fertilizer use (kg NPK/ha)	90-67-0	45-23	45-23
Paddy grain yield (t/ha)			
With fertilizer	5.6	2.1	2.3
Without fertilizer	3.3	1.2	1.3
Stem borer resistance	Comparatively more resistant	Highly susceptible	Highly susceptible
Disease resistance			
Kernel smut	Resistant	Resistant	Resistant
Brown spot (Rati)	Resistant	Resistant	Resistant
Threshability	Hard	Easy	Easy
Grain quality			
Physical (milled rice)			
Average length (mm)	6.4	6.2	6.5
Average breadth (mm)	1.6	1.8	1.7
Average thickness (mm)	1.5	1.58	1.5
Length/breadth ratio	4.0	3.4	3.8
1000-grain weight (g)	13.9	14.0	15.0
Chemical			
Amylose content (%)	22	18	17
Gel consistency (mm)	50	58	52
Gelatinization temperature	I/L	HI/I	HI/I
Protein content (%)	7	7	7
Alkali spreading (%)	7	5	3
Cooking			
Proportionate elongation	1.59	1.52	1.70
Aroma	Strong	Strong	Strong (weak in Sind conditions)
Cooking quality	Good	Good	Good
Eating quality	Good	Good	Good

^a L = low, H = high, I = intermediate.